

Gulf Coast Buff-breasted Sandpiper Survey Protocol - Spring 2016

PROJECT NEED AND BACKGROUND

The Buff-breasted Sandpiper (BBSA) is categorized as “Near Threatened” by IUCN, is included in Appendices I and II of the Convention on Migratory Species of Wild Animals, is a bird of High Concern in the U.S. and Canadian Shorebird Conservation Plans, and occurs on threatened lists in countries throughout its wintering range (Lanctot et al. in press). The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service considers the species as highly imperiled (USSCP 2004) and in need of management attention (U.S. Shorebird Conservation Plan Partnership 2015).

Buff-breasted Sandpipers are thought to have once numbered in the hundreds of thousands; numbers decreased substantially in the late 1800s – early 1900s due to commercial hunting and to loss of habitat along migration routes in the Central and Mississippi flyways of the United States as well as on their wintering grounds in South America (Lanctot and Laredo 1994). The most recent population estimate is only 56,000 birds (range: 35,000 – 78,000, Jorgensen et al. 2008), and survey data from sites on the breeding, migration, and wintering grounds suggest this species is still declining (Lanctot et al. 2010, L. Wolfenbarger, unpubl. data). The most likely impediment to population growth is alteration of grasslands to less sandpiper-friendly habitats along their migration route in the Midwestern United States (Lanctot et al. 2010). However, there is a lack of reliable information on stopover location and turnover rate (needed for accurate and precise population estimates and trends), habitat use, and factors limiting population size. Further, the first population estimate was generated in the Rainwater Basin of Nebraska where likely only a portion of the total population passes through each spring (exact proportion dependent on local conditions). Prior tracking data suggests that the Texas Coast is used by most of the population, making a survey here potentially more informative.

To address these needs, experts who worked on the species in the Rainwater Basin and in other portions of the species range joined interested parties in the Gulf Coast of Texas to form a working group to plan for and develop a ground-survey protocol for conducting a spring and fall migration surveys in 2016. This document lays out the major objectives and methodologies for conducting a Point-count Route style survey and a more focused turf farm survey, which when combined with turnover rate data generated from a companion GPS tagging study, will provide updated population estimates for the species. The spring 2016 survey in the Gulf Coast of Texas will serve as a pilot program that will be improved upon and hopefully repeated during the fall migration of 2016 (and subsequent years if successful), as well as adapted to and expanded to coastal regions of Louisiana in 2017. In addition to learning more about the population size of the species, surveyors will collect data on Buff-breasted Sandpiper habitat use and avoidance. This information will be supplemented with similar, but perhaps less biased data, obtained from GPS tags fitted to birds in coastal Texas in the spring and fall of 2016.

OBJECTIVES

1. Develop and test ground-survey methodology that can be used across Texas and Louisiana to estimate the BBSA population and density at a local scale, so it can be pooled up to larger scales.
2. Estimate population and density of BBSA across a defined area in coastal Texas.
3. Census visible areas of a sub-set of turf farms to estimate a minimum BBSA population and density in selected counties in Texas.
4. Visit and evaluate location of GPS-tagged Buff-breasted Sandpipers when location data become available. Describe current habitat and use expert knowledge to judge what conditions of habitat may have been on the date BBSA were present.

BRIEF METHODOLOGY

- Objective 1: Pilot year surveys using BBS and turf farm complete counts will be tested for their ability to detect BBSA and ultimately to determine density estimates and population sizes within a defined coastal region of Texas and on turf farms, respectively.
- Objective 2: Twelve Point-count Routes were laid out in a randomized fashion in the interior habitats of the Texas Coast. Routes will be surveyed weekly (4 times) between April 15 and May 11, and each route will consist of 45 mile route with 31 stops (points) at 1.5 mile apart and 5 minutes of observation at every point. When encountered on points, the number, distance from the survey point, and habitat used by BBSA and Hudsonian Godwits – another species of concern - will be recorded. The presence of Upland Sandpiper, Pectoral Sandpiper and American Golden Plover will also be recorded. If time permits, the observer will estimate the number of each of these species but this effort should not interfere with detecting BBSA. No data on distance or habitat will be recorded for these species. The top priority of the survey is distance sampling of BBSA and the habitat where they occur.
- Objective 3: A sub-set of the Texas Coastal region’s turf farms will be surveyed during the four sampling periods to provide data on population size and periodicity of use of this habitat type, which is assumed to be used the most by BBSA in coastal Texas. Turf farm surveys are separate but complementary to the point-count routes; 75-80 turf farms in Matagorda, Wharton and Harris Counties will be surveyed in the spring of 2016.
- Objective #4: Forty BBSA will be caught and tagged with GPS-Argos units on Texas coast from April 20 – 30 to help document specific locations used by the species during migration through the Midwest and in the Arctic. Satellite imagery and visits to sites used by individual birds will be used to determine in an unbiased way habitats used and avoided by the species. In addition, location and movements of these individually-tracked birds will identify migration staging areas, turn-over rates at key staging areas, migration paths, and the location of key Arctic breeding sites.

DETAILED METHODOLOGY: POINT-COUNT ROUTES (PCR)

Objective 2

Point-Count Routes

Timing of Sampling and Effort

To establish when to conduct surveys in coastal Texas, we determined the peak dates when BBSA sightings were collected based on eBird data. This indicated dates where 25% of sightings (1st quartile day 110 = Apr 19) and 75% of sightings (3rd quartile day 125 = May 4) occurred. With these dates in mind we defined the survey period as: April 14 to May 11. Four target survey dates, 7 days apart were selected:

- Survey #1: April 15
 - Survey #2: April 22
 - Survey #3: April 29
 - Survey #4: May 6
- a. For every route, the 4 point-count surveys will be conducted on the dates mentioned above if possible (or at least within 3 days of the target date).
 - b. Due to inclement weather, road construction, observer schedule, and other factors it is very unlikely that every survey will be conducted on the established target date (above).

- c. If surveys are delayed, maintain the original schedule for subsequent surveys. For example, if Survey #1 is conducted on April 18 instead of April 15, Survey # 2 still needs to be done on or near target date of April 22.
- d. If a survey is interrupted by change in weather, road conditions (see below for parameters of conducting surveys.) you can stop the route and start the route the next day at the point where you left off. If it isn't possible to complete the survey during the second effort, submit the data collected up to this point. There will be less repetition for some points on that route but the models are robust to unequal samples.

Creating Point-Count Routes

- a. Routes were designed to avoid large blocks of habitat inappropriate for BBSA (forests, shrublands and urban areas) and were constrained to habitat where BBSA are known to occur (agricultural land (crops or pasture) and native grasslands) based on past surveys, e-bird data and expert knowledge. These routes cannot be changed within a migration period but will be assessed for value after each field season.
- b. The start point for most routes is a turf farm or other landscape feature with a history of BBSA sightings (B. Ortego, TXPD data). Albeit not random sampling, this design is used to ensure a minimum of 60 detections (flock = 1 detection, or lone individual = 1 detection) of BBSA are gathered. This is needed to develop a detection function that will help us assess how many birds are being missed. We can also correct for this possible bias in landscape sampling using GIS land cover analysis.
 - a. As of 4/12/2016, 10 of the 12 point-count routes contain at least 1 turf farm; the Egery Flats and Kingsville routes do not.
- c. Routes are on public roads and pre-determined stop points are located where observer can pull vehicle off of roadway. These stop points can also not be changed as the same points must be surveyed during each of the four surveys.
- d. Route direction protocol is adapted from the Breeding Bird Survey (BBS) program. Direction from start point was selected randomly except when start point was at extreme end of survey area (i.e. Matagorda County). Routes continue straight but if route encountered an intersection a random direction to turn was selected. Dead end roads and backtracking were not allowed in route design. Routes do not intersect each other or cross over themselves.
- e. Data from surveys conducted in the 2016 spring pilot season will identify if and how the location, number and design of point-routes need to be modified.

Selection of Points

- a. Points were positioned using Google Earth Pro to locate stops as close to 1.5 mile intervals and as much as possible, to position the surveyor at a site where vehicle can be parked safely from road traffic.
- b. Spatial data (GPS locations) of points and a survey map depicting all proposed survey locations was constructed for each survey route and will be provided to observers prior to conducting the surveys. In this pilot season (spring 2016) each route will be driven before conducting surveys to ensure that the pre-determined points are appropriate (i.e., are in a safe location and have relatively good visibility). If absolutely necessary, the observer can move the point-location by up to 0.2 mile. The GPS location of any modified points will be recorded by observer and provided to "spatial data manager" who will evaluate changes to ensure that the route is still within protocol and will be used as the location for subsequent surveys.

Overview of Point-count Routes

- a. Point-count routes should be run during period of good visibility and with little or no rain. Precipitation limitations identified in BBS protocol will be used (see Appendix X).

- b. **Number of Observers:** Each survey requires only one observer but having two people is allowed. However, to minimize bias in detecting BBSA one person will locate birds and measure distance. The other person can be the recorder and describe habitat. The second person should not locate birds for the first observer. This is important because two people are likely to see more birds than one, making counts between dates not comparable. The distance information being collected by the observers will also help assess detectability. The roles of observer and recorder may alternate between points. If roles alternate, record who observes and who records for each point.
- c. Surveys should start between 7 am to 9 am (no earlier, no later). The observer will select the start time based in part, on the safest traffic conditions. Estimated time to complete route is 4 –6 hours.
- d. Routes will be conducted (driven) in the same direction in each of the 4 surveys.
- e. Each survey point will last 5 minutes unless large numbers of birds are seen (See below for guidelines on how to handle such situations).

Data Collected At Every Point (see methods in next section)

Below is a list of data collected at each point; see below for further description.

1. Date
2. Time (24 hour clock)
3. Wind speed and sky conditions
4. Temperature
5. Waypoint or lat/long of point actually used
6. BBSA flying over or out of area and distance to point (distance only recorded when flying birds observed at start of survey)
7. Number of single BBSA and number of individual BBSA within each flock.
8. Distance from individual BBSA or center of a flock to point.
9. Habitat conditions (vegetation type, height and soil moisture) where each individual or flock of BBSA are seen.
10. Dominant vegetation type, height and soil moisture within each quadrant

I. Conducting Point-Count Routes - General Data Collection Procedure

- a. The observer parks the vehicle at the point and will conduct the survey outside the vehicle. Observations are conducted in 360° from roughly the same point. However observers can cross to the opposite side of road to view that side of the road. The observer should not move up and down field for better vantage point but remain as stationery as possible. The observer documents the waypoint or lat/long (displayed on GPS unit) of where the point was established as a quality-control measure and in case the point is moved due to safety considerations.
- b. Even though points are pre-determined, the observer documents the waypoint or lat/long of the point where they collected data as a quality-control measure and in case the point is moved due to safety considerations.
- c. From the point, the observable area (which is as far as can be seen with binoculars) is visually-partitioned into 4 quadrants.
- d. **To identify quadrants:** The road is the axis. The direction the route is being run is used to identify “right and left”. Front is the direction of the road going to the next point; rear is direction of road to previous site. Quadrants are designated as:
 - i. Right Front (passenger’s side front door)
 - ii. Left Front (driver’s side front door)
 - iii. Left Rear (driver’s side rear door)
 - iv. Right Rear (passenger’s side rear door)
- e. At each point there is a 5 minute observation period for sighting BBSA. Only BBSA present at the beginning of the five-minute observation period are counted.

- f. To comply with distance sampling protocol, when first exiting vehicle, the observer looks for the BBSA closest to the point, either those on the ground or flying out of the point (see g for “sky scan”). Observer looks for BBSA within a 50 meter area circumference around the point (before these birds flush or move in response to observer, etc.). Distance will be measured with the range finder (even BBSA at close range) as well as the habitat the bird is in.
- g. The observer will scan the sky with his/her eyes in very beginning of observation period to locate BBSA flying over-head. The number and distance between flying BBSA and the point are recorded. This initial sky-scan should take less than one minute.
- h. BBSA flying into the point after the first sky-scan but within the five minute observation period are considered incidentals (because they were not there when observer first arrive). If time and interest allow, these data can be recorded in the corner of the field labeled: “numbers of BBSA/HUGO arriving/flying over start.”
- i. **Flocks** of BBSA will be documented as a single detection as required for distance sampling. A flock is a fairly subjective term but is defined as a group of individual BBSA that are clustered together. Additionally, individuals that are part of a flock typically move together on the ground as a group and also will fly from one area to another as a group.
- j. Document the (1) number of flocks, and (2) the number of BBSA in each flock. These data are used to accurately characterize detectability.
- k. **Distance Sampling:** Distance data to individual and flocks of BBSA will be collected to model a detection curve to subsequently account for undetected individuals.
 - Distance data will be recorded within each quadrant
 - When there are lone individuals, measure and record distance to single individuals.
 - When there are flocks, measure and record the distance to the centroid of a flock. The center (centroid) of the flock is where the majority of the birds occur.
 - **The habitat type each individual or flock is in must be recorded** (see habitat types below)
- l. During PCRs documenting data on BBSA is the priority, however if there is time, and **Hudsonian Godwits (HUGO)** are present in the 4 quadrants, document the number, distance to point and habitat on same data sheet used for BBSA.
- m. It is very important that the observer is at the point for the entire five minutes – even when the habitat seems inappropriate for BBSA (tall vegetation, etc.).
- n. If an observer is at a point with a lot of BBSA and the five minutes elapse before finishing, the observer will finish collecting the data on those BBSA (i.e., counting them, recording distance etc.) within 400m of the point. Note on data sheet that this occurred and the time taken for point.
- o. Documenting data on BBSA is the priority, however if time allows, the presence and number of other shorebird species of management and conservation concern (Upland Sandpiper, American Golden Plover, and Pectoral Sandpipers) is documented. This information will help inform use of areas surveyed.
- p. Record the gps location, weather, and habitat type of each quadrat when the survey is completed.

II. Conducting Point-Count Routes – Habitat Collection

The current knowledge is that BBSA generally use certain habitats along the Texas coast such as turf farms and rice fields. However information on the relative use of various habitats, how regional weather patterns (e.g., wet or dry years) influence habitat use, and if the species is avoiding particular habitats is limited. It is also possible that BBSA use habitats that do not have many, if any, eBird sightings since the birding community tend to focus on areas where BBSA have been observed in the past. Thus, the point-count route surveys provide an opportunity to help inform use and avoidance of habitats in an unbiased way (due to the random selection of our survey routes). Additional information on habitat use will be obtained from the GPS tagged birds once the data are downloaded.

- a. Habitat parameters will be documented at every point in every survey by visually assessing the area from the survey point. Observers will not walk in fields.
- b. The observable area at the point will be visually-divided into 4 quadrants see “Id” above.
- c. Record the dominant vegetation type as far as can be seen with the binoculars within each of the 4 quadrants. This information can be collected after the 5 minute observation period.
- d. For each of the 4 quadrants surrounding a point, three measures of habitat will be documented (see Appendix B for codes and examples):
 - The dominant vegetation category. If two vegetation communities seem to be prominent (versus just one), document which category is dominant (occurs in 50% or more of the quadrant) and which is secondary (occurs in 25% of the quadrant).
 - Categories include brush and trees, bare ground, cotton, grain crop (sorghum, corn, wheat), rice, soybeans, turf farm. If a building is present in the quadrant that is also noted.
 - If the species of grass on a turf farm can be detected it is documented. Saint Augustine (fat, waxy/gloss leaf) or Bermuda (thin/wispy leaf).
 - The dominant field or ground moisture:
 - Dry: no water visible
 - Moist: surface is wet but water not visible
 - Wet: surface water in quarter
 - The dominant vegetation height in 4 categories:
 - low: vegetation less than height of BBSA (<8’)
 - tall: vegetation taller than BBSA (>8’)
 - height varies – where there is a lot of variation in height of vegetation (e.g., 25 – 75% of the quadrat is of different heights, not just a couple of bushes in farm field)
- e. When **BBSA (and HUGO) are present, the habitat the bird is in, the height of the vegetation and the soil moisture is also recorded for each bird or flock of birds.** The same codes described above (Appendix B) will be used.

III: Conducting Point-count Routes – Turf Farm Survey

Ten of the twelve PCR routes have a single turf farm included as part of the route that has been selected where a survey of the entire farm visible from the public roads will be completed after the point-count on that farm is completed.

- a. Observers will be provided with a pdf map of the selected turf farm and they will identify (draw on map) the portion they were able to survey. Observers will indicate the area they were able to survey by drawing it on the provided map. On some turf farms, the pdf maps have acres indicated and the observer can note the acres surveyed.
- b. Data will be collected only on BBSA (and HUGO if time and interest allow) and entered on the turf farm field data sheet.
- c. All observations of BBSA will be recorded but there is no need to record distance or habitat use.
- d. If the observer has time and interest at the end of the entire Point-count route, a 2nd survey of that turf farm can be conducted to provide additional data on how birds use the farm throughout the day. This is optional – see IV below.

IV: Conducting Point-Count Routes – Optional Data Collection

To address BBSA temporal use of turf-farms and denoting BBSA use of habitats, the following will be collected if time and conditions allow:

- a. On routes where the ending point is near the starting point of the route and near a turf farm, BBSA in the farm will be surveyed a 2nd time, with the time of day noted. Please use the turf farm survey data sheet.
- b. Incidental sightings of BBSA between points along route: the GPS location, habitat (habitat type, vegetation height and moisture – using same codes in Appendix B), and number of BBSA and HUGO

will be documented (use incidental sightings field data sheet). Given the large number of points, it is important to get the entire route surveyed so don't spend an inordinate amount of time stopping between points. It is more important to get the entire route surveyed then count incidental birds between points.

Training

We will require that all observers participate in a training workshop or webinar. Observers new to point-count routes are encouraged to apprentice with a trained person for one transect prior to conducting a survey. Training is mandatory because (1) the protocol can be difficult to implement in some situations (e.g., turf farms with large numbers of birds), (2) the protocol requires some skills that most people don't practice regularly (i.e., documenting distance to birds), and (3) consistent data collection is essential for the data to be meaningful and ultimately useful.

Equipment

- Vehicle (with good odometer and temperature gauge)
- Map of route, description of all points on route and
- Clipboard
- Hard copies of data sheets: (1) BBSA Map-Style field sheet – see Appendix B; (2) Turf Farm Survey form; (3) turf farm map, (4) Incidental field sheet.
- Binoculars – observer will have to provide. No minimum magnification is required.
- Spotting scope
- GPS unit with waypoints of points/stops and extra batteries
- Range-finder and extra batteries

Description of spring 2016 Routes

Note: Information below may be out of date

Routes had specific starting points and then were randomly positioned following USGS Breeding Bird Survey methodology for establishing roadside routes.

1. Winnie (Jefferson/Chambers/Liberty Co.) Route starts at the one turf farm in Jefferson Co with BBSA sightings in area and randomly traverses survey area.

2. Crosby (East of Houston). Start point was selected at southern most turf farms and randomly traversed lower trafficked public roads in survey area.

3. Katy (NW of Houston). Start point is at only turf farm in area and randomly traversed lower trafficked public roads in survey area.

4-7. Four random routes in Wharton and Matagorda counties (all SW of Houston). These counties were stratified into four segments. The Colorado River was used as the east/west dividing line. North/south division was based on the break in the distribution of turf farms.

4. Eastern Wharton County. For northern route in east segment, one of the three turf farms with consistent BBSA observations was selected randomly as a start point and the route generally traversed northward.

5. Western Wharton County. For west segment, the start point was the one turf farm with reliable numbers and the route randomly traversed the survey area.

6. Eastern Matagorda County

The furthest south turf farm was selected. Route was extended in two random directions. Rules from above used for each direction.

7. Western Matagorda County. The furthest south turf farm was selected as the start point and then the route was randomly positioned.

8. Victoria County. Start point at only turf farm in area with BBSA and then randomly positioned.

9. Egery Flats (W of Rockport). Start point is natural wetlands site where consistent sightings of BBSA occur and then route randomly positioned.

10. Calallen (S of Corpus Christi). Start point is at only turf farm in area and then randomly positioned.

11. Kingsville. Random start point in ag pasture/crop habitat selected and then randomly positioned. May modify if obtain access to King Ranch.

12. Rio Grande Valley. Started at only turf farm within view of public road and then randomly positioned.

Assumptions: *This section will be fleshed out. I would suggest that the assumptions within commonly-used protocols such as distance sampling or Point-count routes don't necessary have to be laid out in this section, perhaps referred to as a citation or in an Appendix. But I think the assumptions we are making that are particular to BBSA in coastal TX in this protocol should be documented in this document – even in rough format for now. For example:*

- a. 7 days between surveys – using common assumption we have about shorebird turn-over rate in Coastal Texas (geolocator data indicated turnover rate may be greater than 7, but based on only 3 birds)
- b. Majority of BBSA that have been reported by birders (eBird) are in turf farms in Texas but we are unsure of the temporal use of turf farms and other habitats.

Assumptions of Density Sampling:

- a. All birds at the point are recorded 100% of the time. Detection of birds away from the point decreases by some undetermined rate that will be modeled with the data collected.
- b. Density is not correlated with distance. In this sampling design, if BBSA avoid or are attracted to roads there would be an underestimate or overestimate of density, respectively.
- c. Variables that may influence detection and/or density (i.e., wind speed and cloud cover) will be recorded (Appendix B).
- d. Distances are measured accurately
- e. Birds are detected at their initial location and have not moved away or toward the observer
- f. Birds in a flock are not independent observations because once an observer sees one bird in the flock, more birds are likely to be detected. Therefore, large flocks are recorded as a single detection. The DISTANCE Program models flock density and flock size to provide a density estimate

MONITORING RESPONSIBILITIES

Data Collection: *This section needs to be further fleshed out*

Biologists from Texas Parks and Wildlife, US Fish and Wildlife Service, Audubon, Coastal Bend Bays and Estuaries Program, Inc., Gulf Coast Bird Observatory, Houston Audubon, Texas A&M Kingsville, citizen scientists from Texas Master Naturalists, ADD

Data Compilation and Analysis:

- After each survey the observer will email, text or call Brent Ortego with the following: date survey was completed and the number of BBSA observed. These results will be tallied and distributed to observers to keep energy revved and identify problems.
- Field data sheets (BBSA map-style) will be saved and sent to LaReesa Wolfenbarger. Each observer will enter survey results onto excel data sheets and email to LaReesa Wolfenbarger. excel datasheet.
- Data from surveys #1 and #2 will be emailed to LaReesa by May 8th 2016 to allow for a general analysis so results can be incorporated into FWS Science Support Program (SSP) proposals (Region 2 is due June 3, 2016).
- Spatial data (locations and points on routes) will be managed by Brent Ortego through field season. Managing these data and other similar duties can be done by Kammie Kruse (USFWS R2 migratory birds) if the team decides that is helpful. Also, Sarah Saalfeld (USFWS R7 migratory birds) can do spatial mapping and archiving of points if needed.

Report Development and Distribution: *We will assign team members to these tasks*

- *Report lead with input from team members especially those conducting data analysis*
- *Who will report be distributed to?*

TIMING AND FREQUENCY

Data Collection: *Section in draft format.*

- Pilot year of field data collection will be in spring migration: April 15 – May 15, 2016. It is anticipated that survey routes will be conducted again in fall of 2016 as well as in both migration periods in 2017 (and perhaps subsequent years). After data from pilot seasons are analyzed we will re-convene to evaluate and determine if data will be collected in 2017 and beyond.
- Information on habitat conditions at locations used by GPS-tagged BBSA will occur in June 2016 where possible. Remotely accessed data will occur throughout summer.

Data Analysis:

- Data from survey numbers 1 and 2 will be analyzed for inclusion in SSP proposals (Region 2 is due June 3, 2016).

Report Development: May 15 – June 30, 2016

Monitoring Related Issue to Consider: *will be fleshed out*

References

APPENDIX A: DISTANCE SAMPLING OVERVIEW

Distance sampling is a method for estimating detection probability. The idea behind it is that it is harder to detect birds that are far away compared to the closer ones. The figure below shows this with the yellow data bars, and the black bars reveal what the actual number of birds would be if the observer had perfect ability to detect birds irrespective of distance.

The observer collects data on the distance to each individual (or flock in the case of BBSA*). Using the distance data, one can model the detection curve (in red) in order to account for the undetected individuals.

Two key assumptions:

1. There is 100% detection at 0m. The observations closest to the observer have the largest effect on the density estimate. If it is unreliable, the estimate is biased in the direction of the observer's error. When training volunteers, stressing the importance of starting surveys with very careful, close observations are really important.

2. Density is not correlated with distance. For our sampling design, if birds avoid roads or were attracted to roads there would be an

underestimate or overestimate of density, respectively.

3. Birds are detected at their initial location and have not moved away or toward the observer. This is basically a variant of #1 except it applies to distance other than 0.

4. Distances are measured accurately.

*When there are flocks like with migrating BBSA, the observer records the distance to the centroid of the flock and the flock size. Birds in a flock are not independent observations because once an observer sees one bird in the flock, more birds are likely to be detected. The analysis reports flock density and flock size and multiplying those gives us a density.

Observer(s): Wolfenbarger Date: 13 Apr 2016

APPENDIX B: BBSA POINT-COUNT ROUTE SURVEYS - GULF COAST - SPRING 2016

Distance
Distance to center of flock at 1st sighting.
Record distance in meters or note otherwise.

Waypoint
The waypoint or lat/long where you collected data.

- Quadrants**
- LF LEFT FRONT
 - LR LEFT REAR
 - RR RIGHT REAR
 - RIGHT
 - RF FRONT

Birds: B = Buff-breasted Sandpiper; H = Hudsonian Godwit

12891
PvD

#: 01

8
0

HABITAT
Dominant = >50% of quadrant; Secondary (if it occurs) = >25% of quadrant

- Vegetation Types**
- B brush and trees
 - b bare ground
 - C cotton
 - G grain = corn, sorghum, wheat
 - P pasture = grasslands
 - R rice
 - S soybeans
 - T turf farm (type unknown)
 - T (s) turf farm (St. Augustine - has fat, glossy/waxy leaf)
 - T (b) turf farm (Bermuda Grass - has thin, wispy leaf)
 - BLDG building

Height

- low: < 8 inches (< ht of BBSA)
- t tall: > 8 inches (taller than BBSA)
- v varied height = 25-75% made up of vegetation of different heights

Moisture

- D Dry
- M Moist - water visible
- W Wet - water standing of surface

Examples of habitat code

(#1) rice field with tall vegetation and damp surface = RtM; (#2) turf farm with 1" vegetation and dry = TID
 (#3) Pasture with varied height (cows grazing so patches of vegetation height) = PvM;
 (#4) if two vegetation types occur in quadrant (and 1 is 60% and is dominant and the other is 40% and is secondary): TID; PvM

TIME = 24 HOUR

02

Wind: 0 1 2
Sky: 0 1

WIND SPEED = BEAUFORT SCALE

- 0 smoke rises vertically (< 1 mph)
- 1 wind direction shown by smoke drift (1-3 mph)
- 2 wind felt on face; leaves rustle (4-7 mph)
- 3 leaves, small twigs in constant motion (8-12 mph)
- 4 dust rises; small branches move (13-18 mph)
- 5 small trees in leaf begin to sway (19-24 mph)

SKY

Conditions

0 = clear or few clouds
 1 = party cloudy or variable
 2 = cloudy or overcast
 4 = fog or smoke
 5 = drizzle
 8 = showers

	Dom	Sec	BLDG
			Y/N
LF	BtD	Ø	N
RR	BtD	Ø	N
RR	(T/s)RM	bØW	N
LR	(T/s)RM	Ø	Y

art
25B

For each detection, record species (B or H), # of individuals, distance, and habitat (type, height & moisture).
 in pasture
 record distance in meters
 scan sky
 you

#: 17 AMGP#: 200* PESA# Ø

*estimated due to time

CODES

Distance

Distance to center of flock at 1st sighting.
Record distance in meters or note otherwise.

Quadrants

LF LEFT FRONT
LR LEFT REAR
RR RIGHT REAR
RF RIGHT FRONT

HABITAT

Dominant = >50% of quadrant; Secondary (if it occurs) = >25% of quadrant

Vegetation Types

B brush and trees
b bare ground
C cotton
G grain = corn, sorghum, wheat
P pasture = grasslands
R rice
S soybeans
T turf farm (type of turf unknown)
T (s) turf farm (St. Augustine - has fat, glossy/waxy leaf)
T (b) turf farm (Bermuda Grass - has thin, wispy leaf)
BLDG building

Height

l low: < 8 inches (< ht of BBSA)
t tall: > 8 inches (taller than BBSA)
v varied height = 25-75% made up of
vegetation of different heights

Moisture

D Dry
M Moist: surface wet but water not visible
W Wet: surface water in quarter

Example of habitat code

(1) rice field with tall vegetation and damp surface = RtM; (2) turf farm with 1" vegetation and dry = TID
(3) two vegetation types in quadrant (1 is 60% and the other is 40%): TID; PtW

WIND SPEED = BEAUFORT SCALE

0 smoke rises vertically (< 1 mph)
1 wind direction shown by smoke drift (1-3 mph)
2 wind felt on face; leaves rustle (4-7 mph)
3 leaves, small twigs in constant motion (8-12 mph)
4 dust rises; small branches move (13-18 mph)
5 small trees in leaf begin to sway (19-24 mph)

SKY Conditions

0 = clear or few clouds
1 = party cloudy or variable
2 = cloudy or overcast
4 = fog or smoke
5 = drizzle
8 = showers

SPECIES

B Buff-breasted Sandpiper
H Hudsonian Godwit